

Enabling access to weather, climate and oceanographic data across institutions: Synthesis report

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Introduction

In Australia, research in the atmospheric, oceanographic and climate sciences is conducted by many organisations, including federal and state government agencies, universities and, in some cases, private companies, and provided with computational support by others. One obstacle to the efficient conduct of this research is the sharing of research data between institutions.

This synthesis report suggests how sharing of research data between institutions can be improved. The authors have drawn on a report ([Enabling access - Report](#)) that was conceived at a workshop held at the Australian Meteorological and Oceanographic Society (AMOS) Annual Conference 2021. The full report describes in detail insights from ten case studies of initiatives that have tackled, or are tackling, issues involving sharing research data across institutions, both in Australia and overseas (see Table 1 of [Enabling access - Report](#)).

This synthesis provides additional discussion of the challenges and suggestions on how to overcome them. This Synthesis aims to provide the basis for collaboration between the climate research and data provider communities for better data sharing.

Recommendations

The recommendations of the report relate to the following areas.

Community approach to data management

At present, there is considerable duplication of datasets between different data-hosting institutions, and it is sometimes unclear to creators of datasets where they should house their data. Data creators should store their data at a host that is recognised by the community as specialising in the relevant data type.

Data-hosting institutions should perform annual audits of their data holdings and make updated data catalogues visible to other institutions so that duplicates can be identified. However, a key improvement would be to make catalogues at different data-hosting institutions interoperable. This would reduce the need for storage of duplicate data and allow data at different institutions

to be searchable by users in single, federated search operations. Efforts towards this goal include the creation of the [Australian Climate Data single access group catalogue](#), which combines records from NCI, CSIRO and the Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN) catalogues as well as user-created records. Full interoperability of catalogues could be achieved by applying a standardised **common data model** across all institutions. This would necessitate the rigorous application of standard metadata and conventions to datasets, and it is recommended that existing widely-used open-source standards like CF be adopted.

In addition to enhancing metadata to accommodate a common data model, other **metadata** improvements are recommended. Metadata should contain information about the provenance and currency of datasets and data creators should ensure that software used to generate data is discoverable via the metadata, or located with the data if this is not possible (see "[Climate Data Guidelines](#)" in the Australian Climate Data Guide). At present, applying metadata can be an onerous task for researchers. Skilled data curators should be available to assist them in this task. Where possible, curator expertise should be embedded in models, post-processing software and workflow engines that auto-generate metadata to reduce the metadata workload.

User-centric data provision to improve accessibility

To enable researchers to make use of shared data between institutions, data hosts should ensure **data access** is intuitive, and that data can be accessed and subsetted remotely on a 24-7 basis (e.g., via APIs). Data should be provided in accessible formats (using appropriate standards where they exist) with tools provided to access, subset, reformat and **process** on-the-fly (e.g., see "[Working with big/challenging data collections](#)" in the Australian Climate Data Guide). This may require data hosts to provide compute resources close to data to reduce the need for data transfer between institutions. The data provision should meet the needs, capabilities and expectations of the intended data users.

To optimise the provision of shared data services, data hosts should **track data usage** and monitor usage patterns and use the insights gained to inform their policies on data storage (e.g., quick- vs slow-access storage) and data retirement. While data creators should ensure that their datasets have DOIs assigned to them, and data users should be encouraged to cite datasets, it should be recognised that citations are not a direct proxy for data value. Tracking data usage and assessing value will require effort from suitably skilled personnel. However, the benefits would be a firmer basis for cases for funding data management and more efficient use of existing resources.

In addition to enhancing tracking of data usage, data hosts should **engage** with the research community more broadly using community forums and other online resources, as well as in person engagement via workshops and hackathons. They should have continuous engagement with the research community and review their data holdings, catalogue search design, systems, processes and personnel skills to ensure that they continue to be fit for purpose.

Resourcing and Funding

Considerable gains in cross-institutional data sharing may be made with a more strategic and coordinated approach to data management. However, effective cross-institutional data sharing does not “come for free” and will not arise through sole reliance on researchers themselves to properly manage their data.

Institutions hosting data should **employ data curators** specialising in weather, climate and oceanographic data to help apply relevant standards, review datasets prior to publication and provide support to both data users and contributors and liaise with the other climate data providers. Skilled data curators are also essential for application of a common data model, tracking of data usage and community engagement.

Funding for data coordination, curators and storage should be recognised as an **ongoing investment** that will yield returns in terms of more effective cross-institutional data sharing. Business cases for funding can be facilitated by better coordination and better assessments of the value and impact of sharing datasets.

Data governance, integrity and security

Improvements to **data governance, integrity** and **security** can build trust in datasets and the systems hosting them, reducing one of the barriers to cross-institutional data sharing.

Data revision and version deprecation procedures in the climate science community require improvement to help build trust in datasets and the conclusions drawn from them, which are becoming increasingly important for decision makers. These procedures may leverage enhanced tracking of data usage to ensure that users are kept abreast of retractions, revisions and updates.

Ethical considerations should be promoted and adhered to when the sharing of data is potentially sensitive (e.g., the CARE principles relating to Indigenous data governance).

Data service providers should consider cybersecurity considerations and solutions to maintain open access to data without compromising host or user security (e.g., common authentication mechanisms).

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